

Supplementary material: Fusion Transformer with Object Mask Guidance for Image Forgery Analysis

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1. Experimental Setup

1.1. Image Forensics Algorithms

In our evaluation, we consider only methods with publicly available code in order to fairly evaluate them under the same setup. We employ as inputs to our score-level fusion network, *OMG-Fuser_S*, the SPAN [11], MVSS-Net++ [2], CATNetv2 [17], TruFor [8] and IFOSN [33] algorithms, due to their competitive performance and their complementarity with respect to the type of artifacts they detect, i.e., artifacts in the RGB domain, edge artifacts, compression artifacts, noise artifacts, and robustness against on-line sharing operations, respectively. Moreover, we utilize the Noiseprint++ [8] and the DCT-domain stream [17] as inputs to our feature-level fusion network, *OMG-Fuser_F*, two learnable forensic signals that captures noise-related and compression-related artifacts, respectively. For all the aforementioned methods, we utilize the official code implementations provided by the original authors.

1.2. Datasets

To train our *OMG-Fuser* models, we utilize data from three publicly available datasets. We randomly sample 25k forged and 25k authentic images from the synthetic dataset used by CAT-Net [16] due to the big variability of its samples regarding compression qualities and depicted topics. We enrich this set with another 10k inpainted images sampled from the DEFACTO [24] dataset. Also, we include all images from the CASIAv2 [3] dataset into our training set to compensate for low-resolution and low-quality images. We utilize 90% of these data for the actual training of the model and the rest 10% for validation purposes. Despite some datasets consisting of more samples, we observed in our experiments that a further increase in the amount of training data did not yield any significant performance increase. Thus, our architecture requires significantly less training data than the previous state-of-the-art ones [8, 17]. Instead, as highlighted by [8], introducing more variability into the training data was more beneficial. For evaluation,

	Dataset	Forged	Authentic	Types
Train	Tampered-50k [16]	25k	25k	SP, CM
	DEFACTO-INP [24]	10k	-	INP
	CASIAv2 [3]	5k	7k	SP, CM
Test	CASIAv1+ [2]	920	800	SP, CM
	Columbia [10]	180	183	SP
	COVERAGE [30]	100	100	CM
	NIST16 [7]	564	560	SP, CM, INP
	OpenForensics [18]	19k	-	SP
	CocoGlide [8]	512	512	INP
	DID [32]	6k	-	INP

Table 1. Number of samples and types of forgery included in the train and test datasets. SP stands for splicing, CM for copy-move and INP for inpainting.

following [8, 11, 21], we have selected five popular datasets, namely the CASIAv1+ [2], COLUMBIA [10], COVERAGE [30], NIST16 [7], OpenForensics [18] datasets, including common cases of image forgery. In contrast to previous works [11, 21], we benchmark our methods on the entire evaluation dataset without making any further assumptions about the type of forgery or utilizing subsets of them. Furthermore, to take into account deep-learning based inpainting operations, we further employed the recently introduced CocoGlide [8] dataset and the deep-learning based inpaintings of the DiverseInpaintingDataset (DID) [32]. A summary of all the datasets used in our research is presented in Tab. 1.

1.3. Implementation Details

We implement and train all of our models using PyTorch [27]. Following [25, 31], we train our models for 100 epochs using the SGD optimizer with momentum [22] set to 0.9. We initialize the learning rate to 10^{-3} , with 5 epochs of linear warm-up and a cosine decay until 10^{-6} . We empirically tune the weights of the optimization criterion and set them to $a = 0.3$, $b = 0.45$, $c = 0.25$. To acquire the instance segmentation masks, we utilize the Segment Any-

	Approach	CASIAv1+	Columbia	Coverage	NIST16	OpenFor.	CocoGl.	DID	Overall
Feature Fusion	PSCC-Net [21]	83.4	86.7	69.3	50.2	51.3	84.1	58.5	70.7
	SPAN [11]	64.2	88.6	78.6	56.6	39.0	82.7	45.9	71.3
	IFOSN [33]	87.4	86.9	63.4	71.1	49.3	79.9	37.8	73.4
	MVSSNet++ [2]	80.0	81.6	80.0	73.1	48.1	83.3	41.5	75.1
	CATNetv2 [17]	87.6	<u>91.7</u>	79.0	68.9	66.3	80.3	80.0	77.2
	TruFor [8]	<u>89.6</u>	90.5	<u>83.9</u>	<u>74.5</u>	<u>71.2</u>	<u>85.6</u>	66.5	<u>77.8</u>
	OMG-Fuser _F (Ours)	92.0	94.6	88.3	82.1	82.0	87.7	<u>78.9</u>	80.1
Score Fus.	DST-Fusion [6]	89.3	91.8	76.6	56.0	33.3	86.5	64.8	77.4
	OW-Fusion [1]	89.1	<u>94.7</u>	82.0	72.5	66.9	84.2	<u>78.2</u>	81.9
	AVG-Fusion	<u>90.9</u>	94.4	<u>87.8</u>	<u>80.4</u>	<u>70.9</u>	87.8	77.5	<u>84.3</u>
	OMG-Fuser _S (Ours)	92.2	96.6	89.3	83.7	85.2	<u>86.2</u>	86.1	86.8

Table 2. Comparison on image forgery localization. Pixel-level F1 scores, calibrated with the best threshold per image, are presented for each algorithm and dataset. The best value per column is highlighted in bold, and the second best is underlined.

thing Model (SAM) [13], a zero-shot model that is not limited to a fixed set of object classes. Furthermore, for the RGB stream, we employ the DINOv2 model [26], trained in an unsupervised manner on a large curated dataset and capable of extracting rich features suitable for a large number of downstream tasks. We utilize its ViT-S/14 variant. During the training of score-level fusion models, DINOv2 remains frozen and the resolution of inputs to all streams is 224×224 . For feature-level fusion models, we increase the input resolution of all streams to 448×448 and fine-tune the DINOv2 backbone in order to capture low-level cues in finer detail. Following [15, 19], we freeze the patch-embedding layer during fine-tuning. For the computation of the input signals, the image is provided in its original resolution to all the respective algorithms.

The number of layers of each stage is set to $B_1 = B_2 = B_3 = 6$. Regarding the localization head, it consists of five upsampling layers, each including a transposed convolution [23], a ReLU [14] activation, and a Batch Normalization [12] layer, with a sigmoid activation at the end of the network. For the detection head, we employ a four-block transformer [4] with a classification token $z^{cls} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ that is used for forgery detection. After propagating through the network, the refined token passes through a single fully-connected layer with a sigmoid activation to generate the final image-level forgery detection score.

The training data are augmented using resizing, cropping, flipping, and rotation operations. Training is performed on a single HPC cluster node equipped with four Nvidia A100 40GB GPUs, with an effective batch size of 160 images for score-level fusion models and 40 for feature-level fusion models. The training requires about 30 hours for the score-level and 60 hours for the feature-level fusion models. Moreover, the stream expansion experiments are performed on a single A100 to better represent a constrained environment. Finally, all the evaluation experiments are be-

ing conducted on a single Nvidia RTX3090 GPU.

For comparison with other score-level fusion approaches, we employ the OW-Fusion [1], a deep learning-based fusion approach, and implement it with the same input signals used on OMG-Fuser_S. Furthermore, in order to take into account the previous statistical fusion frameworks, we reimplement a DST-based fusion framework [6, 28] in Python, using again the same inputs with our score-level fusion implementation. Finally, we use the average of all input signals as a baseline approach.

2. Additional Experiments

Image Forgery Localization on best threshold: Following [8], we conducted additional experiments on image forgery localization, computing the F1 metric for the best threshold per image as an indicator of the performance of the method when properly calibrated. The results are presented in Tab. 2. Similar to the results in the main paper, both our methods outperform the competing approaches from the state-of-the-art in both feature- and score-level fusion with a clear margin.

Instance Segmentation Models: To better evaluate the modularity of our architecture, starting from the trained models of our score- and feature-level fusion implementations, we replaced the instance segmentation masks generated by the SAM [13] with the ones computed by the EVA [5]. In particular, we considered three different types of instance segmentation masks: i) from an EVA model trained on COCO [20], ii) from an EVA model trained on LVIS [9] and iii) from aggregating the segmentation masks of both of the aforementioned models. The results of these experiments are presented in Tab. 3. They highlight that replacing the instance segmentation model used during training has only a minimal impact on performance. This allows the combination of our model with class-specific

Figure 1. Explainability analysis. The top “initial” row of each sample presents the signals fused by OMG-F_S , while the bottom “fused” row presents the Grad-CAM overlay on top of them. Red regions in the overlay maps denote the regions of the signals with the greatest impact on the fusion process. The most-right column depicts the predicted output of our network on top and the ground-truth mask on the bottom row.

Seg. Model		Loc.		Det.	
		F1	AUC	F1	AUC
Feat. Fus.	EVA (LVIS)	66.1	90.5	80.7	87.5
	EVA (COCO)	66.5	90.7	80.3	87.9
	EVA (COCO+LVIS)	67.0	91.3	80.8	88.0
	SAM (SA-1B)	67.3	91.5	82.4	88.0
	Score Fus.	EVA (LVIS)	68.4	92.6	81.9
	EVA (COCO+LVIS)	68.8	93.0	82.4	88.6
	EVA (COCO)	69.1	93.0	81.8	88.4
	SAM (SA-1B)	70.4	93.5	83.2	89.5

Table 3. Comparison with different instance segmentation models. The average pixel-level F1 and AUC scores are reported across all evaluation datasets. The training dataset of each instance segmentation model is reported in parentheses.

segmentation models that better fit the needs of the downstream application.

Computation Time: In Tab. 4, we present the computation time required for extracting the input signals for both our score- and feature-level fusion implementations. The experiments have been conducted on the NIST16 dataset

Signal		Time
Feat. Fus.	DCT [8]	75 ms
	Noiseprint++ [8]	115 ms
	SegmentAnything [13]	1.4 s
	OMG-Fuser_F (Ours)	32.3 ms
Score Fusion	SPAN [11]	1.34s
	IFOSN [33]	6.85 s
	MVSSNet++ [2]	221 ms
	CATNetv2 [17]	1.04 s
	TruFor [8]	1.18 s
	SegmentAnything [13]	1.4 s
OMG-Fuser_S (Ours)	40.4 ms	

Table 4. Computation time for the fused signals and our proposed network. The input signals utilized in the proposed feature- and score-level fusion implementations are considered.

due to its great variability in the sizes of the included images. Our proposed fusion networks impose a minimal overhead on the overall computation time compared to the computation time required for generating the fused signals.

Additional qualitative evaluation: Finally, we present

an extensive qualitative evaluation of our score- and feature-level fusion implementations with several forged and authentic samples in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively. In forged samples, our models greatly improve the localization mask, while in authentic samples, they considerably decrease the false positives.

3. Explainability

To better understand which parts of the input signals contribute the most to the fused tokens \bar{z}^{ft} (eq. 5), we employ the Grad-CAM [29] method. In particular, we compute the gradients of the fused tokens with respect to the $N + 1$ different inputs to the TFT in z (eq. 4) in order to isolate the token fusion process and determine from which tokens the information propagates to the next stages. We compute the gradients based on the output of the TFT, using the squared ℓ^2 -norm of the \bar{z}^{ft} . In these experiments, we employ the OMG-Fuser_S variant of our architecture due to the easier interpretation of the input signals. The explainability maps for three samples are presented in Fig. 1. Our architecture has learned to attend to the correctly estimated regions in the input signals based on the ground truth while ignoring the regions of the input signals containing erroneous predictions. Also, our network focuses on the signals that better capture the forged and the authentic regions separately, e.g. on MVSSNet++ for the detection of authentic regions, while exploiting information from the image to resolve ambiguity in the input signals.

4. Discussion on Research Ethics

Our primary ethical consideration while carrying out this research has been the potential for misuse of the proposed method. In particular, as with any image forensics method, the outputs of forgery localization and detection may be misinterpreted by non-experts or misused by malicious actors in an effort to discredit online digital media as being “manipulated”. This is especially true for methods that result in high false positive rates. Given that OMG-Fuser exhibits consistent improvements in detection accuracy with the integration of additional input forensic signals and demonstrates very low false positive rates, we expect the risk of misuse to be negligible, while at the same time, it enhances the current capabilities of detecting forged online content aimed at spreading disinformation.

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Figure 2. Additional qualitative evaluation results on forged images. From left to right, the image in question, the ground truth mask, the outputs of five recent methods, and the outputs of the two variants of our architecture are displayed.

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Figure 3. Additional qualitative evaluation results on authentic images. From left to right, the image in question, the ground truth mask, the outputs of five recent methods, and the outputs of the two variants of our architecture are displayed.

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